

ITERATION PROCEDURE FOR THE PREDICTION OF RESIDUAL PROPERTIES OF POLYMER BASED STRUCTURAL COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Composite systems with a polymeric phase have a global, anisotropic, viscoelastic-viscoplastic behaviour. The coexistence of elastic and viscoelastic-viscoplastic phases, function of the degree of bonding between the phases, introduces stress transfers between phases even under constant external loadings. Due to the different properties of the phases the environmental conditions induce local stress concentrations. Under those conditions damage initiation and propagation is completely different from the behaviour of an homogeneous, even anisotropic, continuum.

In order to design a structural component based on such a composite for an imposed life time, it is necessary to have not only a data basis of the instantaneous properties but also their time dependency. Such a data basis can be obtained by short term test results under influence of accelerators of the material behaviour, such as temperature, stress level, moisture diffusion and others. Material property maps can be obtained by generalised superposition principles.

Starting from the instantaneous properties a first design can be performed. Based on the property maps an updating of the original design can be worked out till the imposed life time is obtained.

GLOBAL TIME DEPENDENT BEHAVIOUR

Polymer based composite systems exhibit global time dependent stiffness - compliance and strength - limit properties. The design of a polymer based structural component today has to guarantee safe residual properties after an imposed life time. This is the reason for a specific

durability analysis. Many different polymer based composite systems exist today. Others, with different properties of phases and interphase relations, will appear in the future. It is important to identify "accelerators" of the material properties in order to be able to extrapolate long term behaviour under "normal" conditions of the "accelerators" from the short term results obtained under high level of those "accelerators".

Such "accelerators" may be some environmental factors such as temperature and moisture diffusion, or mechanical conditions such as high stress levels or high frequency fatigue tests.

The relation between short term behaviour under high values of the "accelerators" and the long term behaviour under normal values of those accelerators is of the same type of relation as expressed by the classical Time-Temperature Superposition principle, (WLF - master curve) accepted for simple thermorheological continua.

End of the seventies H.F. Brinson and co-workers, [1.1-1.4], proposed to apply to polymer matrix composites some generalised superposition principle known as Time-Temperature-Stress Superposition Principle (TTSSP). This work was further developed by D. Morris, D. Dillard and C. Hiel, [2]. Some extensions to biaxial stress states, R. Brouwer, [3], and to thermoplastic matrix composites, X. Xiao, [4.1-4.2] were developed in Brussels in co-ordination with H.F. Brinson.

A basis for those superposition principles can be found in the work of R. Schapery, [5.1-5.2]. His single integral nonlinear viscoelastic constitutive equations are convenient for the analysis of the influence of stress level, temperature and other environmental conditions on the nonlinearizing functions.

The function controlling the "shift" of the time dependency, related to the entropy, see Fig. 1, is in most applications to polymer based systems, the most sensitive of those nonlinearizing functions.

Figure 1. One dimensional Schapery model.

g_0 : nonlinearity of the elastic modulus

g_1 : nonlinearity in the transfer $Q \rightarrow \hat{Q}$

g_2 : nonlinearity of the thermodynamic modulus unit

a_G : nonlinearity of the thermodynamic storage unit

a_D : nonlinearity of the thermodynamic dissipation unit

$a_\sigma = \frac{a_D}{a_G}$: shift factor

$d\psi = \frac{dt}{a_\sigma}$

$$\varepsilon(t) = g_0 (\dots) S_0 \sigma(t) + g_1 (\dots) \int \Delta S \frac{\psi}{d\psi'} \frac{d(g_2 \sigma)}{d\psi'} d\psi'$$

For laminates the long term behaviour is predicted for an unidirectional reinforced lamina. Those results are introduced in a laminate theory for a long term prediction of the behaviour of a laminated structural component, see e.g. M. Tuttle and H.F. Brinson, [6].

For filament wounded pipes or for pultruded beams the basic short term tests have to be performed on representative reduced models by application of the rules of dimensional analysis with special attention to the effects of upscaling.

Interactions between loading modes and environmental variations accelerating the damage development, and lowering the life time has to be carefully investigated.

The results of such interactions between mechanical cycling and thermal cycling were presented by M.E. Tuttle and A. Pasricha, [7.1-7.2].

Our group, in collaboration with the composite research group of the University of Patras (Greece) and Porto (Portugal), working on unidirectional reinforced laminates Fibredux 920-C-TS-5-42 (Ciba-Geigy), with Torayca 300B fibers, is studying the interaction of dynamic, low frequency, and creep tests, in tension, compression and bending, [8].

LOCAL TIME DEPENDENT EFFECTS

Many fibers can be considered as elastic, or elasto-plastic. The polymer matrix is viscoelastic. If the adhesion between the fibers and the matrix is perfect, we have along the interface $\varepsilon_f = \varepsilon_m$. If $\varepsilon_{comp} = \varepsilon_f = \varepsilon_m = cte$ we realise the conditions of a relaxation behaviour so that a certain amount of the stresses induced instantaneously in the matrix, is taken over, function of time, by the fibers. Such stress transfers were predicted, and measured experimentally, in reinforced concrete in the sixties.

We have discussed a possible simple modelling of this phenomena for polymer matrix composites in 1990, [9].

The stress transfers in a lamina between matrix and fibers, also occur between lamina in a laminate, function of the angle between the elastic directions of the two lamina. For $\theta = \frac{\pi}{2}$ the elastic direction of one lamina correspond to the viscoelastic direction of the other lamina.

As consequence, function of the interaction level between the lamina, we have stress transfers from one lamina to another in an anisotropic way. In a general laminate we will have important or negligible stress transfers between lamina, function of the stacking sequence and function of the interphase properties between those lamina.

In a lamina, and between lamina, weak interphases result in small stress transfers in opposition to strong interphases.

Those local internal, time dependent behaviour may act by the cycling as a "fatigue" source for damage initiation and accelerate damage development.

LOCAL, INTERNAL STRESS CONCENTRATIONS

The simultaneous presence in a composite system, or multimaterial system, of phases with different hygrothermomechanical properties will create stress concentrations under influence of changing environmental conditions. Those cycling stress concentrations, in combination or not with the stress transfers, have also an influence on the damage propagation in the composite system.

LIMIT BEHAVIOUR

The characteristics of the limit behaviour, rupture stresses, and or limit stresses, in a continuum with a viscous component are also time dependent. In order to be able to perform a design for safe residual behaviour after an imposed life-time we have to model the time dependency of the limit stresses and to verify experimentally the conservative degree of this model.

Another possibility is to introduce in a composite laminate theory some assumptions, simulations, of damage development obtained from non-destructive analysis by methods such as ultrasonics or thermomechanical techniques.

VISCOELASTIC - VISCOPLASTIC BEHAVIOUR

If we obtain after creep recovery a residual strain starting from a creep behaviour with an horizontal asymptote, as given in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Creep and creep recovery curves

We have to include some time dependent, or plastic, component in order to model this behaviour. Such plastic modified Schapery behaviour was observed by Tuttle and Pasricha, [7], and by X. Xiao, [10], on Peek composites.

During our experimental testing of Torayca 300B fibre reinforced laminates Fiberdux 920-C-TS-5-42 we have also observed this plastic component, and it was necessary to introduce, as supplementary parameter, the residual plastic deformation ϵ_p , in order to model the creep and creep-recovery behaviour as indicated by Qin Yang, [11].

ITERATION PROCEDURE

The instantaneous properties of the composite are introduced in one of the available composite design codes. Based on a large series of short term tests maps for stiffness-compliance and strength-limit properties are generated, function of time, temperature and other loading conditions. An updating of the results of the design code is performed with the properties after a given time increment. If the results are acceptable the same procedure is used for further time increments.

If the results are not acceptable the initial design is changed till a safe result is obtained for that life-time. It is perfectly possible that as consequence of these changes of the initial design based on the use of the property maps we arrive at an overconservative design. Real time tests on some reference structural components have to validate this entire procedure.

CONCLUSION

Predicted time dependent material properties can be included in an iterative design procedure in order to obtain safe residual structural behaviour for an imposed life time.

Real time test results, on well defined polymer based structural components, are needed in order to have reference data to validate proposed predictive design methods. Those real time reference data must be part of a large international test program if we want to have a sufficient number of test data.

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